

Table SM4. Relative abundance (%) of the three top taxa of the benthic macrofauna from Santos Basin and the São Paulo Plateau along the Transects A-H, arranged from south to north, from 400 to 2400 m depth. For Annelida: (P) Polychaeta; Crustacea: (T) Tanaidacea, (I) Isopoda; Mollusca: (B) Bivalvia.

	400 m	700 m	1000 m	1300 m	1900 m	2400 m
Transect H	Paraonidae (P) 15.9% Magelonidae (P) 11% Syllidae (P) 9.0%	Spionidae (P) 14.6% Cirratulidae (P) 8.6% Syllidae (P) 7.4%	Spionidae (P) 10.8% Syllidae (P) 9.2% Amphinomidae (P) 6.5%	Spionidae (P) 12.4% Syllidae (P) 8.6% Typhlotanaiidae (T) 7.7%	Spionidae (P) 14.3% Sabellidae (P) 9.0% Cirratulidae (P) 8.7%	Spionidae (P) 20.8% Paraonidae (P) 8.0% Cirratulidae (P) 7.2%
Transect G	Paraonidae (P) 23.7% Spionidae (P) 11.1% Pilargidae (P) 8.7%	Spionidae (P) 13.5% Paraonidae (P) 12.7% Cirratulidae (P) 6.7%	Spionidae (P) 12.2% Syllidae (P) 9.3% Paraonidae (P) 9.3%	Spionidae (P) 26.8% Amphinomidae (P) 8.5% Sabellidae (P) 5.9%	Spionidae (P) 10.8% Cirratulidae (P) 8.2% Sabellidae (P) 5.6%	
Transect F	Kelliellidae (B) 13.4% Spionidae (P) 7.7% Pilargidae (P) 7.2%	Spionidae (P) 11.4% Paraonidae (P) 9.6% Cirratulidae (P) 7.0%	Spionidae (P) 13.7% Amphinomidae (P) 9.1% Paraonidae (P) 6.0%	Spionidae (P) 16.2% Amphinomidae (P) 7.4% Cirratulidae (P) 6.9%	Spionidae (P) 14.2% Cirratulidae (P) 13% Colletteidae (T) 5.9%	Sabellidae (P) 18.3% Spionidae (P) 14.3% Cirratulidae (P) 10%
Transect E	Paraonidae (P) 18.7% Pilargidae (P) 10.1% Spionidae (P) 8,7%	Spionidae (P) 15% Paraonidae (P) 13.7% Yoldiidae (B) 6.5%	Spionidae (P) 16.7% Amphinomidae (P) 8.9% Cirratulidae (P) 5.2%	Spionidae (P) 16.9% Amphinomidae (P) 10% Ampharetidae (P) 5.0%	Spionidae (P) 16.4% Paraonidae (P) 8.2% Colletteidae (T) 7.3%	Spionidae (P) 17.2% Sabellidae (P) 14.9% Orbiniidae (P) 5.2%
Transect D	Pilargidae (P) 13.7% Paraonidae (P) 13% Spionidae (P) 9.4%	Spionidae (P) 10.9% Syllidae (P) 7.9% Paraonidae (P) 7.8%	Spionidae (P) 12.1% Cirratulidae (P) 7.8% Paraonidae (P) 7.3%	Spionidae (P) 15.8% Amphinomidae (P) 12% Paraonidae (P) 7.8%	Spionidae (P) 12.1% Sabellidae (P) 8.2% Ampharetidae (P) 5.8%	Sabellidae (P) 23% Spionidae (P) 9.2% Cirratulidae (P) 4.9%
Transect C	Paraonidae (P) 14.3% Nereididae (P) 10.9% Syllidae (P) 8.1%	Paraonidae (P) 17.1% Spionidae (P) 10.4% Cirratulidae (P) 8.7%	Spionidae (P) 11% Cirratulidae (P) 10.5% Amphinomidae (P) 7.4%	Spionidae (P) 15.3% Sigalionidae (P) 5.7% Typhlotanaiidae (T) 5.0%	Spionidae (P) 12.4% Cirratulidae (P) 7.4% Paraonidae (P) 5.0%	Spionidae (P) 11.2% Desmosomatidae (I) 9.0% Sabellidae (P) 8.0%
Transect B	Pilargidae (P) 11.8% Paraonidae (P) 11.6% Nereididae (P) 9.5%	Paraonidae (P) 18.5% Spionidae (P) 12.5% Colletteidae (T) 5.0%	Spionidae (P) 13.9% Amphinomidae (P) 10.3% Paraonidae (P) 7.4%	Spionidae (P) 15.2% Amphinomidae (P) 7.5% Colletteidae (T) 5.3%	Spionidae (P) 19.2% Cirratulidae (P) 10% Desmosomatidae (I) 5.2%	Spionidae (P) 16.7% Sabellidae (P) 12% Cirratulidae (P) 6.7%
Transect A	Pilargidae (P) 16.6% Paraonidae (P) 13.9% Oligochaeta 9.0%	Paraonidae (P) 11% Sigalionidae (P) 6.9% Ampharetidae (P) 6.2%	Spionidae (P) 19% Cirratulidae (P) 7.7% Paraonidae (P) 6.1%	Spionidae (P) 20.5% Amphinomidae (P) 7.2% Colletteidae (T) 6.6%	Spionidae (P) 14% Cirratulidae (P) 9.2% Paraonidae (P) 7.4%	Spionidae (P) 15.8% Sabellidae (P) 10.1% Syllidae (P) 5.7%